

EFFECT OF FOLIAR APPLICATION OF MICRONUTRIENT GRADE XI ON YIELD AND NUTRIENT UPTAKE BY BT-COTTON ON INCEPTISOLS

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Abstract

The present investigation titled "Effect of foliar application of micronutrient grade XI on yield and nutrient uptake by Bt-Cotton on Inceptisols" was undertaken at Research Farm, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola, Maharashtra, during kharif season 2023-24. The experiment was laid out in Factorial Randomized Block Design with three replications and eight treatments. Level of fertilizer (soil application) 100 % and 75 % RDF and micronutrient grade XI foliar spray was applied two times at grand growth stages (45 DAS and 60 DAS) of crop @ 0 %, 0.5 %, 1.0 % and 1.5 % level. Foliar spray of micronutrient Grade XI was given at 45 and 60 DAS (Two sprays). Application of 100 % RDF along with 2 sprays of 1.5 % micronutrient grade XI at 45 DAS and 60 DAS significantly increased the seed cotton yield, cotton stalk yield, uptake of nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium and zinc, iron, copper, manganese and boron as well as chlorophyll content in Bt-cotton. There were significant improvement in soil available NPK content with the application of 100 % RDF, after harvest of crop.

Keywords: Micronutrient, growth, uptake and bt-cotton.

Introduction

Cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) is an important commercial crop grown in various regions for its high quality fiber and oil. It is globally playing a vital role in the agricultural and industrial economy by providing raw materials, particularly for the textile industry, and employment. Globally, it was grown on 33.1 million hectares, yielded 136 million bales, and produced about 35% of the total fiber during the year 2020 (FAO 2021). India achieved 1st place in the world in cotton acreage with 120.69 Lakh Hectares area under cotton cultivation i.e. around 36% of world area of 333 Lakh Hectares. Around 67% of India's cotton is grown on rainfed areas and 33% on irrigated area. In terms of productivity, India is at 38th rank with yield of 510 kg/ha. It provides raw materials for the textile industry which is the largest agro-industrial sector of India. Cotton is one of the most important commercial crops cultivated in India and accounts for around 25% of the total global cotton production. It plays a major role in sustaining the livelihood of an estimated 6 million cotton farmers and 40-50 million people engaged in related activity such as cotton processing & trade. The Indian Textile Industry consumes a diverse range of fibers and yarns and the ratio of use of cotton to non-cotton fibers in India is around 60:40 whereas it is 30:70 in the rest of the world. Due to its economic importance in India, it is also termed as "White-Gold". In Bt cotton due to synchronized boll development rapid translocation of nutrients toward bolls from the leaves occur causes deficiency of nutrients that's why it is necessary to supply optimum amount of macro and micronutrients to maximize the yield of Bt cotton (Hebbar *et al.* 2007).

Effects of foliar application of micronutrients on cotton yield and fiber quality have been widely studied. Generally, the plant requires a wide variety of elements to improve the growth and yield. Boron and Magnesium are the essential elements required for the growth and development having specific role in cell division and cell metabolism. In cotton, flowering is a continuous process. However, all the flowers produced are not retained and harvested. The role of micronutrients in various physiological and biochemical processes in plant is well known, which enables a rapid change in the physiology of plant within one season to achieve desirable results. The essential mineral elements which are required in higher concentrations by the plant have major role in determining the growth and development cotton often produces more vegetative growth, than needed for maximum boll production and yield especially when climatic condition favour vegetative growth, these by directing the nutrients and photo assimilates towards vegetative growth rather than reproductive growth.

Foliar application can be used to improve the efficiency and rapidity of utilization of a nutrient urgently required by cotton crop for maximum growth and yield. A major component of profitable cotton production is adequate and balanced nutrition. Sound cotton fertilization practices ensure improved economics of production, efficiency of nutrient use, and environmental protection. Foliar nutrition serve as a supplement to traditional soil applied fertilizer for sufficient supply of nutrients to cotton crop. Keeping in mind the struggle between plants for getting more plant nutrients, it will be essential to find out the appropriate method of micronutrient application and achieve the maximum yield under rainfed condition. Accordingly a field experiment carried out.

Materials and Methods

A field experiment was carried out during year 2023-24 at Cotton Research Unit, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola (Maharashtra). The experimental field was leveled and well drained. The soil of the experimental site was belonging to Inceptisols, it was calcareous in nature and moderately alkaline in reaction. The fertility status of the soil indicates that the soil was medium in organic carbon (4.26 g kg⁻¹), low in available nitrogen (165.38 kg ha⁻¹), very low in available phosphorus (11.26 kg ha⁻¹) and very high in available potassium (370.14 kg ha⁻¹) and deficient in available zinc (0.52 mg kg⁻¹).

The experiment was laid out in Factorial Randomized Block Design (FRBD) with eight treatments and three replications. The (PDKV JKAL 116) variety of cotton was sown in kharif season by dibbling at spacing 90×45 cm the seed rate of cotton seed for sowing was 3 kg ha⁻¹. Sowing was carried out in July 2023. The recommended dose of fertilizer of NPK was 90 kg N, 45 kg P₂O₅, 45 kg K₂O per hectare. Half dose of N and total amount of P and K were applied at the time of sowing. Foliar spray of micronutrient Grade XI were given at 45 and 60 DAS (Two sprays). Five plants from each treatment were selected randomly and tagged for recording various observation and yield and yield components parameters. Chlorophyll content were recorded by using SPAD meter. After harvest of cotton, soil samples were drawn at random from the each net plots up to 30 cm depth. The composite samples were prepared, for various analysis of available N, P, K, Zn, Fe, Mg and B by adopting standard methods.

Results and Discussion**Effect of foliar application of micronutrient Grade XI on yield of Bt-cotton****Seed cotton yield and cotton stalk yield**

The effect of foliar application of micronutrient Grade XI along with recommended fertilizer levels on seed cotton and cotton stalk yield is presented in table 1.

Levels of RDF

The data in respect of seed cotton and stalk yield as influenced by the recommended doses of fertilizers was found significant. The result revealed that the application of 100 % RDF resulted in significantly higher seed cotton and stalk yield (24.26 kg ha⁻¹ and 38.01 kg ha⁻¹ respectively as compared to 75 % RDF application (20.53 and 32.02 kg ha⁻¹).

Similar results were obtained by Prakash *et al* (2017) reported a significant higher seed cotton yield with the nutrient level of 125 % RDF as compared to 75 % RDF. However, was on par with 100 % RDF.

Table 1. Effect of foliar application of micronutrient Grade XI on yield of Bt-cotton influenced by different treatments

Tr.N.	Treatment Details	Yield (q ha ⁻¹)		Seed yield	Stalk yield
		Seed Cotton	Cotton Stalk		
Levels of RDF (Soil application)					
M1	100 % RDF	24.26	38.01	---	---
M2	75 % RDF	20.53	32.02	---	---
	SE (m) ±	0.28	0.43		
	CD at 5 %	0.85	1.30		
Levels of micronutrient Grade XI					
S1	0 % (Water spray)	20.57	38.54		
S2	0.5 % Foliar spray	22.23	39.62	8.08	9.48
S3	1.0 % Foliar spray	23.22	40.25	12.90	14.55
S4	1.5 % Foliar spray	23.59	14.43	14.69	17.0
	SE (m)±	0.40	0.90		
	CD at 5%	1.20	2.70		
	Interaction (M × S)				
	SE (m) ±	0.56	0.86		
	CD at 5 %	NS	NS		

Similar results were also noted by Kavva *et al* (2021) yield was significantly influenced with the application of micronutrient. Maximum yield was obtained with RDF along with 0.5% Fe, Zn, Mn at 30 DAS which was significantly superior over rest of the treatments except RDF along with foliar spray of 0.5 % Fe, Zn, Mn at 45 DAS. The highest yield obtained with application of micronutrients along with RDF might be due to increased availability of nutrients in balanced proportion.

Effect of foliar application of micronutrient Grade XI on NPK uptake by cotton crop.

The data pertaining to total nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium uptake by seed cotton and stalk is illustrated in table2.

Effect of RDF levels

The data in respect of total nitrogen uptake by seed cotton and cotton stalk as influenced by recommended dose of fertilizers was found significant. The results concede that the application of 100 % RDF resulted in significantly highest total nitrogen uptake by seed cotton and stalk yield (89.54 kg ha⁻¹) as compared to 75 % RDF application (74 .92 kg ha⁻¹).

Similar results were found by Malode *et al* (2016) stated that highest N uptake was recorded in the treatment containing RDF 100 % , followed by foliar application of urea with DAP 2 % . Uptake of N was significantly increased due to application of fertilizer and foliar spray.

Effects of Micronutrient Grade XI spray

The foliar application of micronutrient grade XI at 1.5 % which were applied at two different growth stage showed significantly highest total nitrogen uptake by seed cotton yield and stalk yield (87.52 kg ha⁻¹). This treatment was followed by the foliar spray treatment at 1.0 % level.(S3) , which was statistically at par with 1.5 % foliar spray application. The lowest total nitrogen uptake by seed cotton and stalk yield was reported with the 0%(water spray).

Effect of Micronutrient Grade XI spray

The foliar application of micronutrient Grade XI at 1.5 % which were applied at two different growth stages showed significantly highest seed cotton yield and stalk yield (23.59 and 37.18 kg ha⁻¹) respectively. The treatment of foliar spray at 1.0 % level (S3), which was statistically at par with 1.5 % foliar application .The lowest seed cotton and stalk yield was recorded with 0 % (Water) spray .There were percent increase in seed cotton yield and cotton stalk yield.

More *et al* (2018) reported that significantly higher seed cotton yield kg ha⁻¹ were reported by the application of 125 % RDF + foliar spray of 0.5 % zinc + 0.2 % boron twice during flowering (60 DAS) and boll development stage (80 DAS) and followed by 125 % RDF + foliar spray of 0.2 % boron and 125 % RDF + foliar spray of 0.5 % zinc.

The interaction effect fertilizer and foliar spray was found non significant.

Similar results were obtained by Deshmukh *et al* (2019). The highest nitrogen uptake was recorded with treatment 100 % RDF + 1 % DAP + 1 % KNO₃ + 1% MgSO₄ + 0.5 % Micronutrient grade II which was significantly superior over rest of the treatments. Lowest uptake of nitrogen was noticed with treatments where only RDF was applied.

Phosphorous uptake by seed cotton and stalk yield

Effect of RDF levels

The data pertaining to total phosphorous uptake by seed cotton and cotton stalk as influenced by recommended dose of fertilizers was found significant. The results revealed that the application of 100 % RDF resulted in significantly highest total phosphorous uptake by seed cotton and stalk yield (27.42 kg ha⁻¹) as compared to 75% RDF application (22.04 kg ha⁻¹).

Similar results were found by Waikar *et al* (2015) the highest uptake of phosphorus were noticed with 100 % RDF and two spray of each starter and booster than other treatments.

Effect of Micronutrient Grade XI spray

The foliar application of micronutrient grade XI at 1.5 % which were applied at two different growth stage resulted in significantly highest total phosphorous uptake by seed cotton yield and stalk yield (26.79 kg ha⁻¹). This treatment was followed by the foliar spray treatment at 1.0 % level.(S3) , which was statistically at par with 1.5 % foliar spray application . The lowest total phosphorus uptake by seed cotton and stalk yield was reported with the 0% (water) spray.

The Interaction effect of fertilizer and foliar spray was found non significant.

Similar results were found by Choudhary, *et al* (2017) the highest uptake of phosphorus was recorded with soil + foliar application (Fe +Zn + B).

Potassium uptake by seed cotton and stalk yield**Effect of RDF levels**

The data pertaining to total potassium uptake by seed cotton and cotton stalk as influenced by recommended dose of fertilizers was found significant. The results showed that the application of 100 % RDF resulted significantly highest total potassium uptake by seed cotton and

stalk yield (71.09 kg ha⁻¹) as compared to 75% RDF application (58.99 kg ha⁻¹).

Similar results were found by Vinayak *et al* (2013) application of 125 % RDF recorded higher uptake of potassium over 100 % RDF among foliar spray of liquid fertilizers foliar spray of micronutrients recorded highest uptake of potassium than other treatments.

Table 2. Effect of foliar application of micronutrient on total nutrient uptake by cotton as influenced by different treatments

Tr.N.	Treatment Details	Total Nutrient uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)		
		N	P	K
A. Levels of RDF (Soil application)				
M1	100 % RDF	89.54	27.42	71.09
M2	75 % RDF	74.92	22.04	58.99
	SE (m) ±	0.99	0.39	0.78
	CD at 5 %	2.99	1.17	2.38
B. Levels of micronutrient Grade XI				
S1	0 % (Water spray)	74.31	21.82	58.37
S2	0.5 % Foliar spray	81.46	24.43	64.45
S3	1.0 % Foliar spray	85.63	25.89	68.09
S4	1.5 % Foliar spray	87.52	26.79	69.27
	SE (m) ±	1.39	0.55	1.11
	CD at 5 %	4.23	1.66	3.36
	Interaction (M×S)			
	SE (m)±	1.97	0.77	1.57
	CD at 5%	NS	NS	NS

Effect of Micronutrient Grade XI spray

The foliar application of micronutrient grade XI at 1.5 % which were applied at two different growth stage showed significantly highest total potassium uptake by seed cotton yield and stalk yield (69.27 kg ha⁻¹). This treatment was followed by the foliar spray treatment at 1.0 % level.(S3), which was statistically at par with 1.5 % foliar spray application . The lowest total potassium uptake by seed cotton and stalk yield was reported with the 0 % (water spray).

The interaction effect of fertilizer and foliar spray was found non significant.

The increased uptake of nitrogen, phosphorous and potassium may be due to the beneficial effect of spraying with micronutrients could be attributed to the role of trace elements on fundamental metabolic reactions and absorption of nutrients.

Effect of foliar application of micronutrient Grade XI on chlorophyll content.

The effect of foliar application of micronutrients Grade XI along with recommended fertilizer levels on total chlorophyll content is presented in table 3.

Effect of RDF levels

The data in respect of total Chlorophyll content influenced by recommended dose of fertilizers was found significant at 60 DAS and 90 DAS. The results revealed that the application of 100 % RDF resulted

significantly highest total chlorophyll content (38.77) at 60 DAS and (45.09) at 90 DAS as compared to 75% RDF application.

Increase in chlorophyll content in cotton leaf might be due to supply of nitrogen, magnesium, phosphorus, zinc, sulfur and other micronutrients by foliar application because magnesium and nitrogen are main constituent of chlorophyll and other nutrients like Fe, Zn and S play an important role in synthesis of chlorophyll although they are not constituent of chlorophyll.

Effect of Micronutrient grade XI spray

The foliar application of micronutrient grade XI at 1.5 % which were applied at two different growth stage showed significantly highest total chlorophyll content (40.22) at 60 DAS and (46.40) at 90 DAS . This treatment was followed by the foliar spray treatment at 1.0 % level.(S3), which was statistically at par with 1.5 % foliar spray application . The lowest chlorophyll content was reported with the application of 0 % (water spray).

The interaction effect of fertilizer and foliar spray was found non significant.

Similar results were obtained by Fahad *et al* (2014) reported that the foliar application of micronutrient FeSO₄.7H₂O, H₃BO₃ and ZnSO₄.7H₂O significantly higher leaf content followed by 2 % FeSO₄ +2% ZnSO₄. These two treatments were statistically alike but different from the rest of the treatments.

Table 3. Effect of foliar application of micronutrient Grade XI on chlorophyll Content (SPAD – Reading)

Tr.N.	Treatment Details	Chlorophyll content	
		60 DAS	90 DAS
A. Levels of RDF (Soil application)			
M1	100 % RDF	38.77	45.09
M2	75 % RDF	36.22	43.33
	SE (m) ±	0.77	0.68
	CD at 5 %	2.35	2.05
B. Levels of micronutrient Grade XI			
S1	0 % (Water spray)	34.38	41.57
S2	0.5 % Foliar spray	37.11	43.47
S3	1.0 % Foliar spray	38.28	45.38
S4	1.5 % Foliar spray	40.22	46.40

SE (m) \pm	1.09	0.96
CD at 5 %	3.32	2.92
Interaction (M \times S)		
SE (m) \pm	1.55	1.36
CD at 5 %	NS	NS

Conclusion

From the experimental results it can be concluded that the application of 100 % RDF along with 2 sprays of 1.5 % micronutrient grade XI at 45 DAS and 60 DAS significantly increased the seed cotton yield, cotton stalk yield, uptake of nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium and zinc, iron, copper, manganese and boron as well as chlorophyll content in Bt-cotton. There were significant improvement in soil available NPK content with the application of 100 % RDF, after harvest of crop.

Application of micronutrients along with RDF might be feasible option to increase the Bt-cotton yield under rainfed condition.

References:

1. **Choudhary, S.K., Jat M.K. and Mathur A.K. (2017)** Effect of micronutrient on yield and nutrient uptake in Sorghum. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry* 2017; 6(2): 105-108.
2. **Deshmukh, A.V., Vaidya, P.S. Deshpande and MB Jadhav (2019)**. Influence of foliar nutrition on leaf chlorophyll anthocyanin pigment and leaf reddening index of BT- cotton under rainfed condition. *J. Pharmacognosy and Photochemistry* 2019, 8(5): 1151-1154.
3. **Fahad, S., Ahmad, K. M., Anjum, M. A. and Hussain, S., 2014**. Effect of Micronutrients (B. Zn and Fe) foliar application on the growth, flowering and corm production of gladiolus (*Gladiolus Grandiflorus L.*) in calcareous soils. *J. Agric. Sci. Tech.*, 16: 1671-1682.
4. **Hebbar KB, Perumal NK, Khadi BM**. Photosynthesis and plant growth response of transgenic Bt cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum L.*) hybrids under field condition. *Photosynthetica*. 2007; 45:254-258.

5. **More, V. R., Khargharate, N.K., Yelvikar, N. V. and Matre, Y. B. (2018)** effect of Boron and zinc on growth and yield of Bt cotton under rainfed condition. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Bioscience* 6(4):566-570.
6. **Malode, K. and Tamgadge, D. B. (2016)** Response of cotton to foliar application of nutrients under rainfed condition. *Journal of Cotton Research and Development* 30 (2):210-213.
7. **Prakash, B. H., 2017**, Response of cotton (*Gossypium spp.*) to nutrient and irrigation levels in Southern Dry Zone of Karnataka. M. Sc. (Agri.) Thesis, Univ. Agric. Sci., Bengaluru, Karnataka. Anonymous. 2018. ICAR-All India Coordinated Research Project on Cotton – PI Annual Report (2018-19).
8. **Pochampally Kavya, Shikha Singh, Narreddy Hinduja, Dhananjay Tiwari, Saivasavi Sruthi . December 2021** Effect of Foliar Application of Micronutrients on growth and yield of Greengram (*Vigna radiata L.*) *Legume Research- An International Journal*, Volume 44 Issue 12: 1460-1464 ().
9. **Vinayak Hosamani, Halepyati A.S., Shashikumar, M., Santhosh, U.N., Nataraja, M. and Manu, T.G. 2013**. Quality, uptake of nutrients and Economics of irrigated Bt Cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum L.*) as influenced by macro nutrients and liquid fertilizers. *Global. J. Biol. Agri. Health. Sci.*, 2 (1): 29 – 32.
10. **Waikar, S. L., Dhamak, A. L., Meshram, N. A. and Patil, V. D. (2015)** Effect of speciality fertilizers on soil fertility, nutrient uptake, quality and productivity of cotton in vertisol. *Journal of Agriculture and Veterinary Science* 8 (2): 76-73.